

Thixotropic Behaviour of Thorium Jellies.

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Prakash and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 587) and Dhar and co-workers (*ibid.*, 1929, 6, 391 ; *ibid.*, 1930, 7, 367,417,591) have described the preparation and properties of thorium molybdate, phosphate, arsenate and other inorganic jellies. The thixotropic behaviour of thorium jellies has been dealt with in this paper.

Thorium molybdate, arsenate and phosphate jellies were obtained metathetically by mixing solutions of thorium nitrate and of the corresponding potassium salt. The jellies were allowed to set in large test tubes. The time when the tubes on inversion did not cause the overflow of the contents was noted. The 'set' jelly was vigorously shaken for about two minutes to ensure complete transformation to the sol form, and the time it took to reset was noted. The observations were repeated and the results found to be reproducible.

Thorium molybdate jelly.—To 10 c.c. of thorium nitrate solution, containing 48.24 g. of the salt per litre, were added varying amounts of 3% potassium molybdate and the total volume was made up to 15 c.c. in each case with water. On mixing the contents, a white opalescent mixture was obtained, which cleared within 3 minutes. It was allowed to stand and the setting time was noted.

TABLE I.

		Time of setting.		
3% Potassium molybdate		3 c.c.	3.5 c.c.	4 c.c.
Original setting	...	40 min.	35 min.	30 min.
After 1st. shaking	...	28	24	22
„ 2nd. „	...	26	20	16
„ 3rd „	...	26	20	16
„ 4th. „	...	22	20	15
„ 5th. „	...	22	18	15

After 5 shakings, the time of setting became practically constant. The jellies exhibited thixotropy even when allowed to age for three days, but the time of setting slightly decreased.

In the following table, 3 c.c. of 3% potassium molybdate were used in preparing the jelly.

TABLE II.

Influence of glycerol.

3 c.c. of 3% potassium molybdate.

		Time of setting.		
	Glycerol	0	1.0 c.c.	1.5 c.c.
Original setting	...	40 min.	85 min.	120 min.
After 1st. shaking	...	28	31	39
„ 2nd. „	...	26	27	27
„ 3rd. „	...	22	25	22
„ 4th. „	...	22	—	22

Glycerine stabilises the sol of thorium molybdate to a marked extent, and thus increases the original time of setting of the jelly, yet the thixotropic time finally appears to be uninfluenced by its presence.

TABLE III.

Influence of glycine.

		Time of setting.		
	Glycine	0	0.5 c.c.	1.0 c.c.
Original setting	...	40 min.	50 min.	56 min.
After 1st. shaking	...	28	50	56
2nd.	...	26	19	25
3rd.	...	22	19	25
4th.	...	22	18	22

The smaller quantity of glycine decreases slightly the thixotropic time, while at higher concentrations glycine appears to behave differently. It markedly increases the original time of setting.

TABLE IV.

Influence of sucrose.

		Time	of	setting.
Sucrose (20 %)		0	1.0 c.c.	2.0 c.c.
Original setting	...	40 min.	42 min.	41 min.
After 1st. shaking	...	28	27	31
2nd.	...	26	24	27
3rd.	...	22	20	25
4th.	...	22	20	25

TABLE V.

Influence of potassium sulphate.

		Time	of	setting.
1.15 N—K ₂ SO ₄		0	0.3 c.c.	0.5 c.c.
Original setting	...	40 min.	27 min.	16 min. (loose jelly)
After 1st. shaking	...	28	11	20
2nd.	...	26	11	15
3rd.	...	22	8	8
4th.	...	22	7	9

The addition of sulphate markedly decreases the time of setting. The jelly obtained is loose in structure when higher concentrations of the sulphate are used. The thixotropic time also decreases. The inconsistency observed with 0.5 c.c. of 1.15N potassium sulphate is possibly to be attributed to the weak and unsteady texture of the jelly, in its presence.

Thorium Phosphate Jelly.

Thorium phosphate jelly was prepared by the addition of varying quantities of 22 per cent. potassium phosphate (KH₂PO₄) to 10 c.c.

of the above mentioned thorium nitrate solution. As before, the total volume was fixed by dilution with water as given in the following tables. The thixotropic time is very short, being only a few seconds.

TABLE VI.

Final volume = 12.5 c.c.

22 % KH_2PO_4 .	Time of setting.
0.5 c.c.	70 min.
0.6	12

These jellies on shaking formed a very viscous sol, which reset within 15 seconds. With dilute jellies the thixotropic time becomes measurable (*vide* Table VII). Glycerine increases the thixotropic time.

Thorium nitrate = 10 c.c. 22 % KH_2PO_4 = 0.5 c.c. Total volume = 15 c.c.

	Original time of setting.	Thixotropic time of setting.
No glycerine ...	1 hr. 39 min.	50 sec.
0.5 C.c. of glycerine ...	2 hrs. 15 min.	2 min.

TABLE VII.

.5 C.c. of the stock phosphate. Total volume = 20 c.c.

22% KH_2PO_4 = .5 c.c.

		Time of setting.	
		without glycerine	with .5 c.c. of glycerine
Original setting ...		2 hrs. 40 min.	
After 1st. shaking ...		10 min.	3 hrs.
2nd. ...		10	43 min.
3rd. ...		10	31
4th. ...		9	21

Thus glycerine increases the original as well as the thixotropic time.

Thorium Arsenate Jelly.

Different concentrations of 18 per cent. potassium arsenate solution were used and the total volume was made up to 12.5 c.c. In the beginning, the mixture is opalescent but clears up in a few minutes. It again develops opalescence, becomes translucent when it has set. In contrast to the others, on further standing, the opalescence increases and the solution may finally become opaque.

As soon as the jelly set originally, it was shaken for about a minute and the opalescent sol thus obtained was again allowed to set and the process was repeated, till a perfectly opaque jelly was obtained which broke on the further shaking (Table VIII).

TABLE VIII.

		Time of setting.		
18 % KH_2AsO_4		1.0 c.c.	1.1 c.c.	1.2 c.c.
Original setting	...	53 min.	42 min.	63 min. (non-homogeneous jelly)
After 1st. shaking	...	7	8	11
2nd.	...	3	6	6
3rd.	...	2½	5	5
4th.	...	2	4	4
5th.	...	2	2	breaks
6th.	...	breaks	breaks	—

TABLE IX.

Influence of glycerine.

 18% $\text{KH}_2\text{AsO}_4 = 1.1$ c.c.

		Time of setting.	
Glycerine		0	0.5 c.c.
Original setting	...	42 min.	82 min.
After 1st. shaking	...	8	7
2nd.	...	6	4
3rd.	...	5	3
4th.	...	4	breaks

Glycerol has got a peptising and stabilising influence on the thorium arsenate sol, but does not enhance the thixotropic time. Possibly glycerine by increasing the time of the original setting helps the ageing of jelly forming elements.

Discussion.

The results recorded in the previous tables show that the thorium molybdate and phosphate jellies are highly thixotropic. Thorium arsenate jellies which develop slight opalescence on ageing exhibit this property only when freshly formed, but afterwards they break up when shaken. The velocity of sol-gel transformation in the case of phosphate jellies is very great, so much so, that in some cases it is almost instantaneous. However, if the jellies are diluted, the transformation proceeds at a measurable speed. In all these cases, the original time of setting is much greater than the thixotropic time.

In previous publications (*loc. cit.*), it has been stated that the formation of jellies is guided by two tendencies of the uncharged particles. When the charge on the colloidal particles is decreased by the adsorption of oppositely charged ions from the electrolytes, the particles tend to agglomerate, and in the case of hydrophilic sols, they simultaneously develop hydration. Where the hydration tendency is most marked, the transparent jellies like thorium molybdate and phosphate are formed, but in cases where the agglomeration tendency is also marked, the opalescent jellies, as in the case of thorium arsenate, are obtained. It appears that with the increase in the agglomeration tendency, the thixotropy decreases and such jellies are liable to break up on shaking.

We have also shown that as the concentration of coagulating electrolytes, that is that of the oppositely charged ions is increased, the jelly forming particles tend to develop more agglomeration, which is exhibited either in the form of the shrinkage of the jelly-forming network, when the phenomenon of syneresis is exhibited or in the development of opalescence. In this communication, we have shown from our results on the influence of potassium sulphate, that with the increase of its concentration, the thixotropic property of the jelly is also decreased. When the higher concentrations of this substance are used, the jelly breaks up on shaking. We are of the opinion that for these reasons, the opaque jellies or the jellies undergoing syneresis will not exhibit thixotropy.

According to von Weimarn (*Rep. Imp. Ind. Res. Inst., Osaka*, 1928, 9, 1), the total amount of water imbibed in a jelly is supposed to consist of (i) interatomic hydration *e.g.*, the water in crystal hydrates, (ii) 'surface hydration', *i.e.*, the water adsorbed on the surface of the uncharged particles, and (iii) 'structure hydration' *i.e.*, water enclosed by the pores of the structural elements of the jelly. It appears that along with other factors, the extent of thixotropy depends upon this structurally imbibed liquid. The shaking of a jelly does not markedly influence the surface hydration, while the structurally imbibed liquid is set free when the jelly is agitated. The thixotropic time appears to be the time taken by the sol, so formed, to resume the former structure of the jelly. It has been observed that the original setting time is by far greater than the thixotropic time. This is easily explained, because the original setting time was the time taken by the jelly forming particles to develop surface hydration on slow neutralisation of the charge and also to develop structure hydration; and it must be greater than the thixotropic time where only the structure is re-developed. This is also clear from the fact that the thixotropic time for a dilute thorium phosphate jelly is greater than for the concentrated one, because in the case of a dilute jelly, the water would be more structurally imbibed.

From the results obtained in this paper, it would be seen that glycerine, glycocoll and to a slight extent sucrose also, act as stabilising agents, while potassium sulphate increases the velocity of the gel formation. Glycerine and sucrose are really peptising agents. They possibly influence the preferential adsorption capacity for various ions. The action of glycocoll is amphoteric. In small concentrations, it slightly decreases the thixotropic time. This is due to the diminution of hydrogen ions in its presence. Freundlich (*Kolloid Z.*, 1928, 45, 348) has also observed that the addition of aminoacids to the ferric oxide sols lowers the hydrogen-ion concentration. But with ferric oxide sols, he observed that glycine has got a stabilising influence, and this he ascribed to the tendency of aminoacids to form complex ferric salts. At higher concentration of glycine, we have also observed that its sensitising influence is markedly decreased. It is probable that such anomalies in the case of glycine are due to its amphoteric nature, and not to complex formation.

The phenomenon of thixotropy does not support the view that

the jellies are formed by the release of supersaturation, as has been advanced by von Weimarn. In fact, the solid masses, however transparent they may be, formed by the release of supersaturation (as the jellies of barium sulphate) cannot be retransformed into the solid state by shaking and cannot slowly build up the structure again.

Summary.

1. Thixotropy has been studied in the case of thorium molybdate, phosphate and arsenate jellies. Molybdate and phosphate jellies are highly thixotropic, while opalescent arsenate jellies are only thixotropic when freshly formed; afterwards they lose this property and break up on shaking.

2. The original time of setting of a jelly has been found to be much greater than the thixotropic time of setting. The thixotropic time attains almost a constant value, if the agglomeration tendency is not markedly developed, while it continuously decreases in the case of the agglomerated jellies as thorium arsenate.

3. The thixotropic time in the case of diluted jellies is greater than in the case of concentrated jellies, because, in the former case, the jelly consists of a larger quantity of structurally imbibed liquid.

4. Thixotropy has been explained on the view of the authors' 'hydration-agglomeration hypothesis of jellies'. On shaking, the structurally imbibed liquid of a jelly is set free forming a dispersion medium for the jelly-forming elements, and thus the thixotropic jellies are transformed to the sol condition. The structure is again developed and the gel is again formed.

5. Glycerol and sugar act as peptising agents and in their presence, the original setting time, as well as the thixotropic time, are increased. Glycocoll acts as an amphoteric substance. In small quantities, it decreases the thixotropic time on account of the diminution of hydrogen-ion concentrations. At higher concentrations, it has got a slight stabilising influence. Addition of potassium sulphate decreases the time of original, as well as, thixotropic setting.

6. The phenomenon of thixotropy cannot be explained on the view that the jellies are formed by the release of highly developed supersaturation, as is thought by von Weimarn.